

A qualitative research questionnaire developed for the post-doctoral internship "Integrated Informatics Education: Attitudes and Digital Competences of Primary School Teachers"

Semi-structured interview questions for primary school teachers. The goal is to interview 10-15 teachers from various Lithuanian schools. The duration of the interview is about 1 hour (remote or live).

The purpose of the interview: to find out the current attitude of Lithuanian primary school teachers about the subject of Informatics in primary education and the intention to integrate/already implemented integration. Identify emerging challenges related to the integration of informatics.

The most important thing is your honest answers and real experience because this is the only way to collect the correct information. This is not a knowledge test but an interview to understand the current situation.

No.	Questions
1.	Maybe your school already teaches Informatics in primary grades (it is integrated)?
2.	If not you, maybe colleagues at school integrate/teach primary school students Informatics? How do you rate their practices?
3.	In which lessons do you integrate/plan to integrate Informatics?
4.	How much time do you spend (plan to spend) on it?
5.	Maybe you have your annual (semi-annual) plan for how and when to integrate informatics; maybe there is a plan at the school level?
6.	What challenges do you think you face in practice when integrating Informatics into your lessons?
7.	How much effort do you personally need to integrate Informatics? <i>Note: Effort is understood through the statement "I am doing the best I can within my abilities."</i>
8.	What do you think encourages/motivates you to integrate Informatics into primary education?
9.	What do you think is the role of your school administration?
10.	Maybe you have support from parents/students?
11.	What opportunities (for your students) do you see when you integrate Informatics into your lessons?
12.	Maybe you have already familiarized yourself with the guidelines for updating the general education curriculum, which talk about integrating Informatics into other areas of education in primary education? What thoughts come to mind?
13.	What prompted you to familiarize yourself with the guidelines for updating the general education curriculum?
14.	Is it easy for you to understand the differences/similarities between the terms mentioned in the guidelines: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • students' digital abilities, • development of digital competence, • digital intelligence, • informatics, • computational thinking.

15.	Which of the following terms is the easiest to understand? Why? What determines this?
16.	<p>Six areas of achievement are distinguished in the guidelines of the primary education Informatics curricula:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Digital content creation, 2. Algorithms and Programming, 3. Data Research and Information, 4. Solving technological problems, 5. Virtual communication and collaboration, 6. Safe behavior. <p>Which areas of achievement do you think are the most difficult to implement? Which are the easiest? What determines this?</p>
17.	What areas of achievement do you think you have the right tools for teaching?
18.	If you already integrate Informatics, what terms/words do you use when talking to students? <i>Eg, Algorithms, Informatics, Automation, Commands, Binary Search, etc.</i>
19.	Maybe you participated in professional development training (seminars, training, courses, etc.) related to the subject of Informatics and its integration.
20.	If you can name which ones? What duration?
21.	Do you think the training was useful? Why?
22.	Do you find information on what methodologies to apply? Where are you looking for it?
23.	Do you have any advice on what methods should be used?
Sociodemographic data	
24.	<p>Where is your school located:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • in a big city (Vilnius, Kaunas, Klaipėda, Šiauliai or Panevėžys) • in the ring municipality (Vilnius region, Kaunas region, Klaipėda region, Panevėžys region, Šiauliai region, Alytus region) • in a city with a population of 20-99 thousand population • in a city with a population of 10-19 thousand population • in the city-municipality center with up to 10 thousand population • in another type of city with less than 10,000 inhabitants. population • in a rural area
25.	School type:
26.	Your age:
27.	<p>Your teaching experience in primary education?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • up to 5 years • 5-10 years • 11-15 years old • 16-20 years old • more than 20 years